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Research Article

CORRECTION OF DISORDER OF THE COHERENT SPEECH OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN WITH THE ERASED FORM OF DYSARTHRIA

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Abstract:

At the present stage of development of defectological science and practice the problem of correction of coherent speech of children with erased form of dysarthria has a great scientific and practical importance. The article theoretically substantiates the program of speech therapy of the correction of speech disorders of preschool children with erased form of dysarthria, as well as experimentally the effectiveness of this program is proved. It is clearly shown that the application of the developed program of correction contributes to the level of development of coherent speech of preschool children with erased form of dysarthria, there is a positive dynamics of change in all forms of coherent speech: phrasal, dialogic, monologue.

Keywords: *comprehensive psychological and pedagogical assistance, children with disabilities, erased form of dysarthria, mental development, coherent speech, correctional and developmental work, correctional and developmental program.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Coherent speech is a speech making activity of the formation and formulation of thought, followed by its expression in speech with precise words in correctly constructed sentences, united in a single semantic and structural whole. This is a complex, multiphase thought process occurring in the inner speech and reflected in the statement. As a product of speech activity, the statement contains the main characteristics of this process: integrity and coherence. In conditions of normal development, the ability of children to formulate a thought integrally and coherently, with new means, regardless of the situation in which they are pronounced, is formed by preschool age. In terms of dysontogenesis, the development of coherent speech is difficult. One of the variants of speech dysontogenesis is dysarthria with the most common erased form.

Dysarthria occurs as a result of disorder of innervation of articulatory organs while the processes of understanding and generation of speech utterance are preserved. The leading speech disorder of dysarthria is phonetic and phonemic underdevelopment. The difficulties of constructing a detailed statement in dysarthria are due not only to motor speech disorders, but also are associated with the difficulty of choosing the right word. Kinesthetic disorder leads to a lack of stability of words, which complicates the preparation of the general scheme of verbal statements and selection of lexical units. Disorder of sound pronunciation in dysarthria becomes the reason of the delay of the rate of overall speech development and underdevelopment of a lexical and grammatical system. In the Russian speech therapy correction of underdevelopment of coherent speech of preschool children with dysarthria is carried out by methods and programs for children with General underdevelopment of speech. Special methods, programs and means of correction of coherent speech with erased form of dysarthria are not presented.

The study of speech disorders of dysarthria is presented in the following works: R. A. Belova-David, S. I. Maevskaya, L. V. Lopatina, G. V. Gurovets, M. M. Kol'tsova, E. M. Mastukova, M. B. Eydinov, E. Ya. Pravdina-Vinarskaya, E. F. Sobotovich, S. I. Maevskaya, R. I. Martynova, L. A. Chistovich, K. A. Semenova, V. A. Kozhevnikova, L. V. Melekhova, N. V. Serebryakova, E. F. Sobotovich, O. A. Tokareva, M. B. Eydinova etc., E. F. Arkhipova, O. V. Pravdina, L. S. Volkova define the main directions of speech therapy. In the complex of correctional work, the following areas are distinguished: the formation of phonemic hearing, the formation of speech breathing, overcoming voice disorders and prosodic side of

speech, the development of articulation and general motor skills, correction of the phonetic side of speech. Practical experience of correction of coherent speech with erased form of dysarthria in our country is not enough.

Dysarthria is studied from the point of view of different scientific approaches: clinical (E. M. Mastukova, M. V. Ippolitova, K. A. Semenova, L. I. Belyakova, N. N. Voloskova), neuropsychological (L. M. Shipitsyna), neurological (I. I., Panchenko, L. A. Shcherbakova), psycholinguistic (E. N. Vinarskaya), psycho-pedagogical (L. V. Lopatina, N. V. Serebryakova, I. I. Mamajchuk, G. V. Chirkina, O. G. Prikhodko, etc.). It determined the existence of several approaches to the classification disorders of dysarthria. Neurological approach of O. V. Pravdina is based on the account of localization of brain damage and disorders of motor functions of speech. Psycholinguistic approach to classification of dysarthria E. N. Vinarskaya is based on the pathogenetic analysis of neurophonetic syndromes of dysarthria and their correlation with the differential topical diagnosis of focal brain lesions. The syndrome approach of I. I. Panchenko is based on the existence of complicated forms of speech disorders such as dysarthria in cerebral palsy.

Dysarthria is a complex speech disorder caused by a lesion of the central nervous system that occurs as a disorder of the motor mechanisms in the pre-speech period of the child's development. The children with dysarthria have a lack of all parts of speech development, and, as a consequence, underdevelopment of coherent speech. Underdevelopment of vocabulary, grammatical system and coherent speech are secondary disorders in the structure of speech defect in dysarthria. The organization and content of speech therapy work on the formation of coherent speech of preschool children with speech disorders is considered in speech therapy in the framework of technologies to eliminate its underdevelopment. Researches of V. K. Vorobyova, V. P. Glukhova, L. N. Efimenkova, N. S. Zhukova, R. E. Levina, L. V. Lopatina, N. V. Serebryakova, L. F. Spirova, G. V. Chirkina are mainly aimed at the study and correction of the primary disorders of dysarthria: phonetic and phonemic underdevelopment. Special methods, programs and means of correction of coherent speech in dysarthria are not developed. Currently, there are no studies that reflect the provision of targeted speech therapy to children with erased form of dysarthria for the correction of coherent speech disorders.

The analysis of theoretical sources and practical activity in the aspect of the developed problem showed that the questions connected with correction of disorders of coherent speech of children with the erased form of dysarthria remain today insufficiently studied area of scientific psychological and pedagogical knowledge and practical activity that allowed to formulate a hypothesis of research of this problem: speech therapy work on correction of disorders of coherent speech at preschool children with dysarthria will be effective provided the use of a special program, including stages and conditions of formation of grammatical skills, skills of dialogical and monologic speech.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

In accordance with the hypothesis, the following tasks were set and solved in the experimental study:

1. To analyze theoretically the main approaches to the problem of correction of underdevelopment of coherent speech of preschool children with erased form of dysarthria.
2. To make a diagnostic complex for the study of underdevelopment connected speech of preschool children with the erased form of dysarthria and to identify the characteristics of underdevelopment of connected speech of preschool children with the erased form of dysarthria.
3. To develop and to test a program for the correction of speech disorders of preschool children with erased form of dysarthria.
4. To evaluate the effectiveness of the program for the correction of speech disorders of preschool children with erased form of dysarthria.

The methodological positions of the study were determined on the basis of the fundamental provisions of domestic psychology about the objective laws of psychological development of normal and abnormal child, the foundation of which rests on the theory of cultural-historical development of higher mental functions and the theory of the unity of thinking and speech, L. S. Vygotsky; theory of the unity of laws of development in terms of speech ontogenesis and dysontogenesis (L. S. Vygotsky, V. I. Lubovsky, G. Ya. Troshin, O. N. Usanova, U. V. Ul'enkova, T. B. Filicheva); the theory of speech activity (L. S. Rubinstein, A. N. Leontiev, A. A. Leontiev, N. I. Zhinkin, I. A. Zimnyaya, etc.); clinical and psychological-pedagogical concepts of the etiology and mechanisms of dysarthria (E. F. Arkhipova, E. N. Vinarskaya, E. M. Mastukova, M. V. Ippolitova);

theory and methodology of speech therapy of dysarthria (E. F. Arkhipova, L. S. Volkova, R. I. Lalaeva, R. E. Levina, L. V. Lopatina, O. V. Pravdina, O. G. Prikhodko, M. E. Hvatzev, etc.).

In accordance with the methodology of the study, the following methods were used: theoretical understanding and analysis of data of psychological and pedagogical studies on the problem of interest; ascertaining experiment, including a battery of methods for the diagnosis of coherent speech of preschool children with an erased form of dysarthria, observation, conversation; quantitative and qualitative analysis of the results; forming experiment, including the development and testing of a program of correction of coherent speech of preschool children with an erased form of dysarthria.

At the ascertaining stage of the study, a battery of techniques for the diagnosis of coherent speech of preschool children with an erased form of dysarthria was developed:

1. The technique of T. B. Filicheva is aimed at the study of dialogic speech: the definition of the ability to answer questions, ask questions, enter into communication [8].
2. The method of compiling the phrase of V. P. Glukhov is aimed at determining the ability to make a statement at the level of a simple phrase: to establish semantic predicative relations independently and transmit them in the form of a phrase corresponding to the structure [2].
3. The methodology of the story based on the story picture of I. L. Baskakova, V. P. Glukhov is aimed at determining the ability to make sentences independently and arrange them in a logical sequence [2].
4. The method of compiling the story on a series of plot pictures by T. V. Akhutina T. A. Fotekova is aimed at determining the ability of orientation and understanding of the situation of the actions depicted in the pictures, the independent construction of the program of utterance and the choice of lexical units, the external motor design of the phrase corresponding to the main stages of constructing a coherent statement [9].
5. The technique of retelling of the text T. V. Akhutina T. A. Fotekova is aimed at defining the ability to find lexico-grammatical forms of expression in the transmission (recognition and retention) of speech information [9].

To select evaluation criteria for all assignments of composed diagnostic methods, we used the dimensional scores of techniques T. V. Akhutina T. A. Fotekova. Independence of the answer, adequacy, grammatical correctness, lexical registration was estimated. To assess the dialogic and monological speech, the criterion of structural and semantic completeness of the answer was additionally used, including the characteristic of the answer by word, phrase, sentence for dialogic speech; and for coherent speech was also used the presence of semantic links and the storyline of the story. Quantitative evaluation of responses was determined by the sum of the test scores for a series of tasks of one block and correlated with the levels of underdevelopment of coherent speech. To record the responses of the subjects, a protocol of examination of each participant indicating the evaluation criteria and a speech card with indicators of ascertaining and control experiment were drawn up.

At the forming stage of the experiment the following materials were used:

1. O. S. Ushakova, E. M. Strunina Methods of speech development of preschool children [5, 6].
2. L. V. Lopatina Overcoming speech disorders of preschool children (correction of erased of dysarthria) [4].
3. E. F. Arkhipova Correctional and speech therapy work to overcome the erased dysarthria of children [1].
4. I. A. Filatova Correction of speech disorders of preschool children with dysarthria [7].
5. S. G. Shcherbak Formation of oral monologue speech of children with minimal dysarthric disorders [10].

The study was a pre-school educational institution in Kirov. The experiment involved 40 children diagnosed with dysarthria with erased form of its manifestation at the age of 6 years.

At the first preparatory stage, the scientific literature on the problem of research was studied and analyzed; the scientific apparatus of the study was determined; the base of the study was determined; the ascertaining stage of the experiment was carried out, the disorder of coherent speech of preschool children with erased form of dysarthria was studied.

At the second stage, a program for the correction of coherent speech disorders of preschool children with erased form of dysarthria was scientifically substantiated and developed; the forming stage of the

experiment aimed at the implementation of the program was carried out.

At the third stage, the control stage of the experiment was carried out, the analysis and processing of experimental data were carried out, the theoretical and experimental conclusions were clarified, the results of the study as a whole were systematized and generalized.

RESULTS:

A study of the condition of the coherent speech of children with the erased form of dysarthria was aimed at the evaluation of such of its manifestations as phrasal speech, dialogic speech, monologue speech.

Evaluation of phrasal speech showed that 40% of preschoolers with erased form of dysarthria had III level of underdevelopment of coherent speech, which corresponds to the expressed degree. In 60% of subjects the level of underdevelopment of phrasal speech corresponds to a moderate degree. Mild degree of phrasal underdevelopment of speech of children with the erased form of dysarthria have been identified.

Evaluation of dialogic speech of preschool children with erased form of dysarthria was carried out on two series of questions: how to answer the questions at the first meeting of the subjects with the experimenter and how to answer the questions after retelling the text "Jackdaw and pigeons". Its estimation of preschoolers with the erased form of dysarthria have not identified a normal level of development of dialogical speech, all subjects were observed in level II, which corresponds to the moderate degree of retardation. Expressed and mild degree of underdevelopment of dialogic speech of children with erased form of dysarthria was not revealed.

40% of children of the experimental group have underdevelopment of monologue speech, corresponding to the expressed degree, 60% of the subjects have the level of underdevelopment corresponding to a moderate degree. A mild degree of underdevelopment of coherent monologue speech was not revealed [3].

Evaluation of the independence of the tasks showed that 80% of the subjects needed help in the form of a leading question that determines the structure of the future statements. 50% of cases of answers to questions on the read text preschoolers with the erased form of dysarthria found it difficult to build an independent detailed statement and needed an additional question. 60% of the children of the

experimental group were unable to determine the sequence of actions depicted in the pictures and needed help in the form of a leading question.

In all forms of coherent speech in assessing the adequacy of the reflection of perception there were no cases of inadequate responses. In this case, all the subjects made statements that do not fully reflect the situation of the story. In their responses, there were semantic substitutions, incomplete sentences, which made it difficult to transfer perception. All of the subjects identified lack of compliance of the formulation of the statements is shown in the picture or plot of the story. Evaluation of the completeness of perception in monologue speech revealed interpretative presentation of the plot pictures of 60% of preschoolers with erased form of dysarthria.

In assessing the grammatical correctness of the answers of connected speech it is revealed that most preschoolers with erased form of dysarthria made mistakes in the use of prefixes, the use of temporary forms of the verb, in the use of suffixes and in the agreement on declension, in the agreement of pronouns with the verb. In the construction of proposals 60% of children with erased form of dysarthria missed the connecting unions, there is an incorrect use of prepositional structures. When constructing sentences, 60% replaced a complex monologue with a sentence with a simple enumeration. 80% of the children in the experimental group had difficulties in making a logical connection between the proposals. 60% of preschool children with the erased form of dysarthria made up of incomplete sentences.

When assessing the lexical design of coherent speech statements, the adequacy of the use of verbal means, the presence of close substitutions, the presence of pauses and forgetting words, the use of adjectives and adverbs were evaluated. In assessing this indicator, it was found that all preschoolers of the experimental group adequately use the word to express their thoughts, but there is an inaccurate use of lexical values, use close semantic substitutions in phrasal, dialogical and monological speech.

Thus, the results of evaluation of the independence of the answer, adequacy, grammatical correctness, lexical design statements coherent speech led to the conclusion that preschoolers with erased form of dysarthria, along with the adequacy of the answers and the adequacy of the use of verbal means, there were difficulties in the preparation of simple and complex phrases, difficulties in the completeness of the perception of the plot images and text, which was manifested in frequent semantic substitutions of verbs

and nouns, interpretative perception of the plot pictures, the difficulties of preserving all the semantic links of the listened text. When composing the story in one scene the picture there were difficulties of an independent programming statements. The underdevelopment of lexical and grammatical components of the language system was revealed in the difficulties of prefixal and suffixal word formation, the coordination of nouns by declension, the coordination of the temporal forms of the verb, the use of prepositional constructions. In the formulation of statements, difficulties were observed in the formulation of complex proposals, which were replaced by a listing of actions in violation of the structure of the proposal and the formulation of a logical connection. All preschool children with dysarthria were observed expressed lack of adjectives and adverbs. The identified difficulties allow us to note that between preschool children with erased form of dysarthria there are both disorders of the processes of understanding of speech communication and speech production, and the logic of the statement.

One of the main tasks of educational institutions is the formation of coherent speech of preschool children, which is an indicator of its intellectual development, logic reasoning, creative potential. Therefore, the purposeful development of coherent speech is crucial in the system of speech therapy work with children, including those with erased form of dysarthria.

The purpose of the program is the correction of disorders of coherent speech (the use of verbal dictionary, dictionary of adjectives, suffixal word formation, prepositional structures, the use of complex logical and grammatical structures, the formation of phrases, the formation of dialogue and monologue speech) of preschool children with an erased form of dysarthria, which is a prerequisite for successful and effective training in mass secondary school.

Speech therapy work, based on the psycholinguistic approach, included the following areas: the formation of the dictionary, the formation of the phrase, the formation of dialogue and monologue speech. The principles of the program were: ontogenetic principle of the appearance of speech forms in the process of development; personality oriented approach; consideration of individual and psycho physiological characteristics of each child.

Correctional and pedagogical work was carried out in subgroup classes once a week for 25 minutes in the morning. The program consisted of a set of classes, divided into the following blocks: 1) the formation of lexical and grammatical skills, 2) the formation of

phrases, 3) the formation of dialogic speech, 4) the formation of monological speech. Speech therapy work was carried out in the following sequence:

I stage – preparatory. The aim of the stage was to achieve the necessary level of speech and language development for the preparation of different types of detailed statements. The tasks of the preparatory stage of training included the formation of lexical and grammatical skills of preschool children with erased dysarthria. At this stage, exercises were included on the formation of a dictionary of verbs and adjectives (formation of the structure of the meaning of adjectives and verbs; formation of semantic fields; formation of contextual meaning and polysemy of verbs and adjectives; development of syntagmatic relations of verbs and adjectives); exercises on the development of word formation (formation of the skill of word formation of the diminutive form of nouns, formation of the skill of word formation of verbs and adjectives); exercises on the formation of the grammatical structure of speech (formation of inflection: mastering prepositional constructions).

Stage II – main. The purpose of the stage was the formation of skills of independent use of individual phrases and logical-grammatical structures, which played a leading role in the development of monologue speech. The tasks of the main stage included the formation of phrasal and dialogic speech, as a compilation of the answer to the question. At this stage, exercises were included on the formation of skills of compiling a simple and complex phrase (making a phrase with the name of the object over which the action is performed; distribution of phrases with adjectives; making sentences with homogeneous subjects); exercises on the preparation of a complex phrase (preparation of compound sentences with double predicativity; preparation of compound sentences consisting of two symmetrical parts with the separating union "a"; preparation of compound sentences, of which the first sentence begins with the word "first", and the second sentence begins with the words: "and then"); exercises on the preparation of complex sentences (construction of a phrase with unions – if, so, though, but); formation of skills of drawing up of the phrase as the answer to the question (exercises on drawing up phrases as the answer to the question of the preset phrases; composing phrases for the noun agreeing with the adjective in gender and number; composing sentences with this word by picture as the answer to the question: "Where? How? Where? When?").

Stage III – the final, the purpose of which was to improve the structure of speech, assimilation of the

rules of construction of sentences and the whole text. The tasks of the third stage included the formation of skills in the construction of the program statements and the choice of lexical and grammatical structures for its external implementation. The exercises on the retelling of a series of story pictures; writing story for a series of genre paintings; the retelling of the text without support on the picture; the retelling of the text according to the story the picture; drawing up the story according to the story the picture were included.

Practical visual and verbal methods were used for the organization of correctional speech therapy. At all stages of training of preschool children with the erased form dysarthria, attention was paid to the selection of lexical means and grammatical registration of the statement.

Control experiment aimed at assessing the effectiveness of the program of correction of speech disorders in preschool children with erased dysarthria, showed that the level of underdevelopment of coherent speech of 40% of the subjects increased to a mild degree of underdevelopment. Their speech was characterized by independence of drawing up answers and unfolding of pictures, the correct lexical and grammatical registration of the statement: the use without errors of prefixal and suffixal word formation, use of prepositional constructions, coordination of words on declension, the use in the speech of adjectives, construction of difficult sentences with preservation of structure and the correct registration of logical communication. The retelling of the text was characterized by the preservation of all semantic links, but the lack of completeness of the transmission of perception of the listened text because of the preserved semantic substitutions. Their stories according to the story the pictures were characterized by the lack of intense and logical because of the difficulties of self-build and retain throughout the story of the program statements.

The level of underdevelopment of coherent speech of 40% of subjects with a pronounced degree of underdevelopment of coherent speech after the formative experiment increased to a moderate degree. The level of underdevelopment of coherent speech of 20% of the subjects has not changed, although there was a tendency to increase indicators within the level (self-preparation of complex phrases, fewer pauses, lexical substitutions, agrammatism).

SUMMARY:

In the course of our experimental study, we found that preschoolers with erased form of dysarthria are able to adequately answer questions, make a simple and

complex phrase, stories on the picture, a series of pictures, retell unfamiliar text. While there have been challenges with the completeness of the transfer of the perception of the story pictures and text, difficult to hold on to all the semantic units of the text listened, difficulties independent of the programming statements. The underdevelopment of lexical and grammatical components of the language system was revealed in the difficulties of prefixal and suffixal word formation, the coordination of nouns by declension, the coordination of the temporal forms of the verb, the use of prepositional constructions. In the formulation of statements, difficulties were observed in the formulation of complex proposals, which were replaced by a listing of actions with disorder of the structure of the proposal and the formulation of a logical connection. All preschoolers with erased form of dysarthria had severe insufficiency of adjectives and adverbs. The revealed violations of development of coherent speech of preschool children with the erased form of dysarthria caused need of development of the program of logopedic work.

For the basis of the development of the program of correction of disorders of coherent speech of preschool children with erased form of dysarthria the psycholinguistic approach is laid, as well as the ontogenetic principle of the appearance of speech forms in the development process, the principle of personality oriented approach, the principle of taking into account the individual and psycho physiological characteristics of each child.

The program was aimed at the formation of the dictionary, the formation of the phrase, the formation of dialogue and monologue speech. The implemented program of correction of violations of the coherent speech of preschool children with the erased form dysarthria based on the results of the control experiment showed the effectiveness of the level of development of coherent speech of preschool children with the erased form of dysarthria increased, there was a positive dynamics of changes in all forms of coherent speech: phrase, dialogue, monologue.

CONCLUSION:

Thus, the study allows us to draw the attention of speech therapists to the need for the organization of psychological and pedagogical assistance to children with dysarthria, not only from the position of correction of primary disorders in dysarthria – phonetic and phonemic underdevelopment. Development and implementation of programs for correction of speech disorders of preschool children with erased form of dysarthria is a promising direction.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

The authors confirm that the submitted data do not contain a conflict of interest.

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